

Recommended citation: Vermeersch, J. (2017). Course and Campus Choice in a Multi-Campus Setting. Factors Influencing Study Choices of (Bio)Engineering Technology Students . In Quadrado, J. C., Bernardino, J., & Rocha, J. (Eds.), *Education Excellence for Sustainability. SEFI 45th Annual Conference* (pp. 1061-1068). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Azores, Portugal. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14698385.

Course and campus choice in a multi-campus setting

Factors influencing study choices of (bio)engineering technology students

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ABSTRACT

As higher education institutions become more competitive in the recruitment of students, the need arises to gain insight into their study choice process. This is even more pivotal for multi-campus institutions, who are confronted with the added complexity of positioning campuses as well as courses. This study aimed to cast light on the factors influencing students' choice of a course and campus. To this end, a survey was conducted in a (bio)engineering technology faculty offering courses at seven campuses, yielding 1.064 respondents and a 94% response rate. Course content, expected career prospects, expected job security, and correspondence to prior education emerged as the most decisive factors for the choice of the course. Campus choice depended on the course offer and range, academic reputation and local scientific research, and geographical proximity. Students from all campuses valued similar course attributes, but different campuses did attract students for different reasons. The majority of students remained undecided until the last year of secondary education; many students even kept several options in mind up until their enrollment. Four information sources excelled at reaching prospective students: the university website, brochures, contacts with family and friends, and info events. Marketing and recruitment recommendations are provided.

Conference Key Areas: Attractiveness of Engineering Education

Keywords: study choice, multi-campus, information sources, recruitment

INTRODUCTION

The choice of a course and campus is a key decision for prospective students and directly impacts higher education institutions (HEIs), as their funding is highly dependent on student enrolment numbers [1]. As institutions become more competitive in the recruitment of students, the need arises to gain insight into their study choice process, so as to attract the right students to the right courses [2,3].

This is true for all higher education institutions but even more so for multi-campus institutions. As a consequence of mergers in tertiary education, multi-campus

institutions are becoming increasingly common. These institutions are confronted with the added complexity of positioning not only their university and courses, but also different campuses. At present, nevertheless, not much is known about how students deal with this aspect nor have there been many studies on why students choose a course in the field of (bio)engineering technology.

This paper therefore aims to answer four research questions: (1) which factors play a decisive role in the choice of a course and (2) of a campus in a multi-campus (bio)engineering technology faculty, (3) when do students make the final choice, and (4) which information sources are most effective in reaching the current generation?

1 GAINING INSIGHT INTO STUDY CHOICES

The process of choosing a course and institution has been the subject of much scrutiny over the past decades, from different perspectives. One of the first articles on college choice warned practitioners not to assume a direct causal link between recruitment strategies and student enrolment numbers. The authors argue that college choice is affected by both individual characteristics and external factors, but mostly indirectly, by influencing the student's perceptions of college quality [4].

Further studies have identified a plethora of influences by elaborating on decision-making models from marketing and sociology. The resulting study choice models can be divided into three categories. A first group embraces economic and econometric models, which operate on the assumption that preferences are based on rational consideration of constraints and benefits. The second type are sociological models, focusing on contextual, cultural and social influences and influencers. The third category contains combined models, focusing simultaneously on rational and subjective forces [3,5,6,7]. A common element in all models is the premise that, after conscious or unconscious consideration of each option's expected costs, perceived benefits and chance of graduating, the aspiring student will choose the options with the best expected outcome [8]. Often cited influencing factors include course suitability, geographical proximity, academic reputation, self-efficacy, graduates' labour market prospects, family, peers, demographic attributes, financial constraints and application procedures [1,4,5,6,8,9,10,11].

The choice process itself has been segmented into three to nine stages [2,3,7]. Information sources relevant to choosing a college or course have been addressed as well, though with inconsistent outcomes [2,4,5,6,9]. For a comprehensive overview of literature on study choice, consult the article by Obermeit [7].

2 METHOD

In this study, all first year undergraduate students of the multi-campus Faculty of Engineering Technology at the KU Leuven university were asked to fill in a paper survey at the beginning of the current academic year ('16-'17). All seven campuses offering a bachelor program in (bio)engineering technology participated in the study.

The paper questionnaire was limited to two pages and consisted of three short sections. The first section focused on choice factors. Students were asked to indicate out of a list of nine factors those that had been decisive in their choice of a course, and to rate the importance of fifteen factors on their choice of a campus on a five-point Likert scale. Answer attributes were obtained from literature or suggested by the faculty board. The items were chosen to reflect different types of motivators: intrinsic interest, social and geographical aspects, educational considerations, and expected benefits on short and long term.

In the second section, a number of questions and statements intended to find out more about the choice process. Students marked which information sources had taught them about the existence of their course, and when they had made a choice.

Finally, background information was collected about their prior education and type of residence (living at home or at a dormitory).

3 RESULTS

A total of 1.064 students filled in the survey, yielding a 94% response rate. *Table 1* provides detailed information about each campus' sample weight and response rate.

Table 1. Number of respondents, sample weight and response rate for each campus.

	N=	n=	% of sample	Response rate
Aalst	32	32	3%	100%
Bruges	88	86	8%	98%
Diepenbeek	183	173	9%	95%
Geel	96	95	12%	99%
Ghent	233	197	19%	85%
Leuven	364	356	33%	98%
Sint-Katelijne-Waver	131	125	12%	95%
Total	1.127	1.064	100%	94%

Considering the high number of respondents and response rate, no additional checks were necessary to estimate the sample's representativeness for the total population.

The paragraphs below explore four research questions:

1. Which factors influence the choice of a course?
2. Which factors influence the choice of a campus?
3. When do students make their final study choice?
4. What information sources are most important to reach prospective students?

Additionally, differences in responses for students with different profiles are reported. The significance level was adjusted to .0045 according to the Bonferroni correction method, but this did not alter any conclusions regarding (non-)significance of results compared to a .05 level as all calculated values were well above or below the threshold.

Prior education was dichotomized into general secondary education (ASO) and technical secondary education (TSO), with a prevalence within the sample of 70% ASO versus 30% TSO. Type of residence was classified as students who live at home (61% of the sample) and students with residence in a dormitory (39%).

3.1 Choosing a course

The findings suggest that the majority of the students felt most compelled to pursue a study in (bio)engineering technology because of their interests and the content of the course, the expected job prospects and the expected job security (*Fig. 1*).

The match to prior education also proved to be an asset for students with a technical secondary education (TSO), but not for students from general secondary education (ASO) (indicated by 64% of students from TSO opposed to 33% from ASO; $\chi^2(1)=88.215$, $p<.001$).

Other factors, such as the university degree, expected salary and opinion of others were reported to have had less influence on respondents' choice.

Chi-square tests of independence showed only minor differences between campuses and no marked differences between the decisive factors for a course in engineering technology compared to bioengineering technology ($p > .05$).

Fig. 1. Decisive factors for choice of course (multiple answers possible).

3.2 Choosing a campus

Fig. 2 shows influences on the campus choice. Most important on average was the possibility to take a specific course ($M=3.58$, 63%), followed by the range of courses ($M=3.09$, 40%), the campus' reputation ($M=3.20$, 47%) and its scientific research ($M=2.79$, 30%). The top five is completed by geographical proximity ($M=2.73$, 36%). Ranking items based on the number of students who scored each item as having a (very) strong influence presents a slightly different picture: in this case, city ($M=2.64$, 30%) gains importance to the expense of scientific research.

Fig. 2. Degree of influence on campus choice.

Looking at campuses' results in detail shows that the course offer is consistently the most important factor, but also illustrates strong differences in items' scores and ranking for each campus separately.

Independent-samples t-tests show only minor differences between students with different prior education, and predictable differences between respondents based on their type of residence. Students who live in a dormitory are far less concerned about proximity ($M_D=1.93$, $SD_D=1.208$; $M_H=3.28$, $SD_H=1.287$; $t(1033)=16.861$, $p<.001$), accessibility by public transport ($M_D=2.21$, $SD_D=1.143$; $M_H=2.66$, $SD_H=1.333$; $t(1035)=5.611$, $p<.001$) or accessibility by car ($M_D=1.58$, $SD_D=.894$; $M_H=2.43$, $SD_H=1.278$; $t(1033)=-11.870$, $p<.001$) compared to students who commute between their homes and campus, but they attach more value to study choices of friends and family ($M_D=2.68$, $SD_D=1.299$; $M_H=2.23$, $SD_H=1.227$; $t(1034)=-5.681$, $p<.001$).

The statement 'I chose a campus first, and a course next' elicited very strong responses from the students. The item was rated on a six-point Likert scale from 'strongly disagree' (1) to 'strongly agree' (6), and generated a mean score of 2,08 ($SD=1,39$). No fewer than 83% of all respondents declared they did not concur. Exactly 50% marked the 'strongly disagree' option, 22% opted for 'disagree' and 11% selected 'slightly disagree'. The percentages on the other side of the scale were 9% for 'slightly agree', 5% 'agree' and 3% 'strongly agree'.

3.3 Timing of the final decision

Most students (90%) did not make a choice until the last year of secondary education. One third (38%) chooses a course before the Easter holidays of sixth grade. Another third (32%) keeps different options in mind until the end of their final term, and the last third (30%) even up until their enrollment in the summer months.

A graphical representation of the collected data suggests a tendency for students from technical secondary education to make the final decision sooner than their peers from general secondary education (Fig. 3). A chi-square test of independence confirms this difference ($\chi^2(6)=20.083$, $p=.003$).

Fig. 3. Timing final study choice

There were no marked differences between students from (bio)engineering technology ($\chi^2(6)=5.324$, $p=.80$), nor between campuses ($\chi^2(36)=37.386$, $p=.41$).

3.4 Information sources

More than half of the respondents has learned about the course through info days or fairs, friends and/or family. Traditional information sources such as brochures and the university website also remain important (Fig. 4).

Less important but still worth mentioning are teachers and study counsellors, who generated awareness about the course and campus for one student out of five. The open course week, an annual event where prospective students can attend a number of classes, has a smaller effect but still manages to reach 14% of all students.

Fig. 4. Information sources relevant in finding out about course offered on campus (multiple answers possible).

One of the most striking observations, however, were the differences between the answers of students registered at different campuses (*Fig. 4*, on the right). This suggests that not all information sources had been equally effective for each campus. For several items the results varied by more than 15% between campuses. The difference was most pronounced for the university website, with percentages ranging between 30% and 61% depending on the campus ($\chi^2(6)=62.110$, $p<.001$). Moreover, the average number of information sources indicated by each student was similar for each campus, as was verified by a between-subjects ANOVA ($M=2.51$, $SD=1.282$; $F(6,1052)=1.194$, $p=.31$), eliminating this as an alternative explanation.

4 DISCUSSION

This paper intended to contribute to a better understanding of the decision-making process of students entering higher education, and specifically of those who wish to pursue a study in (bio)engineering technology in today's multi-campus setting.

Marketing departments will benefit from insight in the study choice process by being able to select the most effective recruitment strategy to attract students to courses and campuses that offer the best fit with their preferences and needs. This in turn will help educational programmes improve retention rates. And faculty and university boards will find useful pointers in the results to keep their educational offer attractive even when presented with budget cuts and restructurings.

4.1 Summary, comparison to prior studies, and recommendations

The findings of our large scale quantitative survey show that course content, expected career prospects, expected job security, and correspondence to prior education were perceived as the most decisive factors for a course in (bio)technology engineering. Other factors, such as the university degree, expected salary and opinion of others were reported to have had less influence. This provides useful recommendations for marketing practitioners. Based on this study, marketing campaigns should be equally effective for all target groups and regions by highlighting these assets. The only exception is with regard to prior education, where it might be interesting to tailor the message so as to reach students from both general and technical secondary education in the most effective way.

The results are mostly in line with previous studies: in our study as well, intrinsic motivation was important, but so were labour market perspectives [2,6,9,10,11]. The opinion of others was considered less important than in prior studies [4,5,9]. Note that subscription fees and application procedures have not been included in our questionnaire, as higher education in Belgium is highly subsidized and the only

requirement for admission to most higher education courses is to have obtained a secondary education degree. The fact that in our study intrinsic motivation was the strongest driver for the course is probably also related to this fact.

The strongest factors determining choice of campus were the campus' specific course offer and range of courses, academic reputation and local scientific research activities, and geographical proximity. In the minds of our students, though, the choice of a course trumped the choice of a campus. Students from all campuses valued similar course attributes, but different campuses did attract students for different reasons, in line with our expectations. This confirms that unique selling propositions do matter for recruitment. Our results correspond most to the college choice factors identified by Stanley and Reynolds [9]. Geographical proximity, which has often been identified as a major influencer [1,6,8], was taken into account by our students, but in comparison to a much lesser degree. This was interesting, as the course in engineering technology is offered at all seven campuses, allowing students to choose a campus based on the distance to their residence. On the other hand, the distance between any two campuses is less than 200 kilometres and Flanders has a dense infrastructural network, which perhaps makes distances irrelevant.

Marketing campaigns need to highlight the right information, but also need to reach students before they have made their decision. Based on the results from this study, the best time to start communicating to prospective students seems to be during fifth grade for students from technical secondary educational and during sixth grade for students in general secondary education. The most crucial moment to reach students is in the weeks before and after the Easter holidays. Even so, info events during the summer months matter as well and are recommended.

Personal contacts clearly played a major role in creating awareness about the course offer. Four information sources excelled at reaching potential students: the university website, brochures, personal contacts with family and friends, and info days or fairs. Contrary to some other studies [5,6], in our study both the website and brochures provided by the HEI had a strong impact. Marketing practitioners are advised to select a diversified communication strategy, as not all information sources seemed equally effective for each target group and region.

4.2 Strengths, limitations and directions for future research

One aspect to keep in mind when interpreting the findings is that all results were self-reported in retrospect. Students might have rationalized their decisions [8], been unaware of the impact of certain influences, or given a false account of their impact. In awareness of these potential limitations, the questionnaire was presented on paper and kept anonymous so as to avoid a social desirability bias.

Asking students about their choices at the beginning of the academic year allowed to take into account the final decision and the process right up until their enrolment. A limitation is that the sample was limited to those students who actually enrolled, a challenge addressed in literature [2]. This did not present an issue, however, because of the large sample and response rate and because the majority of all (bio)engineering technology students in Flanders were still included in this study.

This study extends upon existing literature by adding campus choice. Further research could validate the findings in other countries or fields of study. The author is currently investigating whether choice factors of prospective students match the actual strengths as identified by current third-year students. Additionally, a longitudinal study might be interesting to look into the relationship between choice factors, individual characteristics, study results and graduation rates.

5 ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The author would like to thank Greet Langie, André Lauwers, Geert Van Ham, Dorine Bruneel, Gorik De Samblanx, Jeroen Buijs and Johan Baeten for their advice on the questionnaire and their efforts in collecting the data.

REFERENCES

- [1] Widiputera, F., De Witte, K., Groot, W. and Maassen van den Brink, H. (2017), The attractiveness of programmes in higher education: an empirical approach, *European Journal of Higher Education*, [in press], pp. 1-20.
- [2] Veloutsou, C., Lewis, J.W. and Paton, R.A. (2004), University selection: information requirements and importance, *International Journal of Educational Management*, Vol. 18, No. 3, pp. 160-171.
- [3] Vrontis, D., Thrassou, A. and Melanthiou, Y. (2007), A contemporary higher education student-choice model for developed countries, *Journal of Business Research*, Vol. 60, pp. 979-989.
- [4] Kealy, M.J. and Rockel, M.L. (1987), Student Perceptions of College Quality: The Influence of College Recruitment Policies, *The Journal of Higher Education*, Vol. 58, No. 6, pp. 683-703.
- [5] Maringe, F. (2006), University and course choice: Implications for positioning, recruitment and marketing, *International Journal of Educational Management*, Vol. 20, No. 6, pp. 466-479.
- [6] Simoes, C. and Soares, A.M. (2010), Applying to higher education: information sources and choice factors, *Studies in Higher Education*, Vol. 35, No. 4, pp. 371-389.
- [7] Obermeit, K. (2012), Students' choice of universities in Germany: structure, factors and information sources used, *Journal of Marketing for Higher Education*, Vol. 22, No. 2, pp. 206-230.
- [8] Finger, C. (2016), Institutional constraints on the translation of college aspirations into intentions – Evidence from a factorial survey, *Research in Social Stratification and Mobility*, Vol. 46, pp. 112-128.
- [9] Stanley, G. and Reynolds, P. (1994), The relationship between students' levels of school achievement, their preferences for future enrolment and their images of universities, *Higher education*, Vol. 27, No. 1, pp. 85-93.
- [10] Davies, P., Mangan, J., Hughes, A. and Slack, K. (2013), Labour market motivation and undergraduates' choice of degree subject, *British Educational Research Journal*, Vol. 39, No. 2, pp. 361-382.
- [11] Soutar, G.N. and Turner, J.P. (2002), Students' preferences for university: a conjoint analysis, *International Journal of Educational Management*, Vol. 16, No. 1, pp. 40-45.